

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.495 Max: 62.634	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1230 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropic	 University of Northumbria Northumbria Museum of Archaeology Gabii Project	
				In cross-section? ☐ Yes ☐ No	In elevation drawing? ☐ Yes ☐ No		Photos: ☒ Yes ☐ No #: 1989-1992
DEFINITION slabs above sewer cut into bedrock				Covered by ☒ SU: 1173	Fills ☒ SU: 1230	Filled by ☐ SU:	
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? ☐ Color ☒ Composition ☐ Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS ☐ Accumulation ☒ Construction ☐ Cutting ☐ Erosion ☐ Collapse ☐ Intentional deposition				
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%		
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive Compaction ☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft Color ☐ Black ☐ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)	
☐ Pottery ☐ Tiles ☐ Amphorae ☐ Dolia ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☐ Mortar ☐ Coins ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Glass	☐ Nails ☐ Marble ☐ Quarried debris ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Basalt slabs ☐ Opus signinum ☐ Painted plaster ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Other (specify)	☐ Tufo (specify) ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)	☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☐ Animal bones ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)				
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						Depth: ☒ Original ☐ Not Original	
Northern Limit		Southern Limit		Western Limit		Eastern Limit	
☐ Original ☐ Not Original ☒ Excavation Limit		☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit		☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit		☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit	
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE							
Is equal to:				Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abutted by:				Abuts:			
Is covered by: 1173, 1410!				Covers: 1228			
Is cut by:				Cuts:			
Is filled by:				Fills: 1230			
OBSERVATIONS dry, sunny conditions, SU was discovered in 2010 and more exposed in 2011							
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: southwestern corner of Trench B post 2010 excavation limit along wall 1058 Shape: rectangular, the slabs are not fully exposed, so measurements are quite difficult to gain							
For layers complete this section:							
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):							
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope)							
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):							
Nature of the interface with layer below: ☐ sharp ☐ diffuse ☐ commigled ☐ other (specify)							
For cuts complete this section:				Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):			
Cut edges: ☐ rounded ☐ straight							
Cut sides: ☐ straight ☐ concave ☐ convex ☐ sloping							
Cut bottom: ☐ flat ☐ concave ☐ irregular							
How is cut top edge? ☐ sharp ☐ rounded							
How is cut bottom edge? ☐ sharp ☐ rounded							
Observations:							

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

*tufo slabs of
diff. thickness
and size*

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

INTERPRETATION

*Tufo slabs that cover a drainage channel below the
via Claudia (SU 1400)*

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

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